

WOMEN IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: SCIENCE AND QUALITY EDUCATION

3RD INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

MAZMUN VA TIL INTEGRALLASHGAN O'QUV JARAYONIDA VIDEO MATERIALLARDAN FOYDALANISHNING AMALIY USULLARINI TATBIQ QILISH

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Katta o'qituvchi

Калит видеоматериаллар, ва тил интеграциялашган ўқитиш, амалий қиймат, инновациялар	сўзлар: мазмун	Аннотация: Видео материаллар энди нафақат кундалик ҳаётнинг бир қисми, балки инглиз тилини чет тили сифатида барча талабалар учун синфда ва ундан ташқарида ўқитишнинг самарали усули сифатида намоиш этилади. Технологиянинг доимий ўзгариб бораётган ютуқлари ўқитувчиларга онлайн материаллар ва видеоларни анъанавий синфдаги вазиятларга қўшиш учун янги имкониятларни тақдим этиб, ўрганиш ва ўқитишни янада қизиқарли ва мазмунли қилиш имконини беради. Видео материалларнинг катта афзаллиги шундаки, улар асл ва ҳақиқий маълумотларни тақдим этади, чунки улар дастлаб она тилида сўзлашувчилар учун яратилган, масалан, филмлар, турли теледастурлар, қўшиқлар. Видеолар турли хил ўқув ва ўқув муҳитларида мазмун ва тилни интеграциялашган ўрганиш синфида, шунингдек, контентни тақдим этиш, муҳокамани бошлаш, муайян мавзулар ва мазмунни кўрсатиш, ўз-ўзини ўрганиш ҳолатлари ва баҳолаш усулида амалга оширилиши мумкин.
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IMPLEMENTING THE PRACTICAL TECHNIQUES FOR VIDEO IMPLICATION IN CONTENT AND LANGUAGE INTEGRATED LEARNING

Key words: video materials, content and language integrated learning, practical implication, innovation

Abstract: Video materials nowadays are not only part of everyday life activities, but they are shown as an effective method in teaching English language as a foreign language for all learners both inside and outside classroom. Ever-changing technological advancements present new opportunities for instructors to incorporate online materials, videos into traditional classroom situations, allowing both learning and teaching to become more interesting and meaningful. A great advantage of the video materials is that they provide original and authentic input as they are produced originally for native speakers such as films, different TV programs, songs,. Videos can be implemented in variety of instructional and teaching settings in content and language integrated learning classroom as well, as a way of presenting content, initiating discussion, for providing illustration for a certain topic and content, self-study and evaluation situations.

ВНЕДРЕНИЕ ПРАКТИЧЕСКИХ МЕТОДОВ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ВИДЕО В СОДЕРЖАТЕЛЬНО-ЯЗЫКОВОМ ИНТЕГРИРОВАННОМ ОБУЧЕНИИ

Ключевые слова: видеоматериалы, содержательно-языковое интегрированное обучение, практическое значение, инновации

Аннотация: Видеоматериалы в настоящее время являются не только частью повседневной жизни, но и показаны как эффективный метод обучения английскому языку как иностранному для всех учащихся как в классе, так и за его пределами. Постоянно меняющиеся технологические достижения предоставляют преподавателям новые возможности для включения онлайн-материалов и видео в традиционные классные ситуации, позволяя как обучению, так и преподаванию стать более интересными и содержательными. Большим преимуществом видеоматериалов является то, что они обеспечивают оригинальный и аутентичный ввод, поскольку они созданы изначально для носителей языка, таких как фильмы, различные телепрограммы, песни. Видеоролики могут быть реализованы в различных учебных и учебных условиях в классе интегрированного обучения по содержанию и языку, а также как способ представления контента, инициирования обсуждения, иллюстрации для определенной темы и контента, ситуаций самообучения и оценки.

When teachers bring video materials into their English classrooms, students can directly acquire a great amount of cultural background information and emotional attitudes about the learning materials. Therefore, they could employ

their autonomy in language learning. While viewing the video materials, students can put themselves in the vivid atmosphere created by the video materials and understand the pragmatics of the language used by the characters.

According to Tomalin's (1981 p.12) research, language teachers like video because it motivates learners, brings the real world into the classroom, contextualizes language naturally and enables learners to experience authentic language. Students like it because video presentations are interesting, challenging, and stimulating to watch" Video also can be more motivating than other forms of authentic material. Christopher and Ho (1996, pp. 86) provide another reason why this is so; it can be entertaining. Music and setting elements can make for an enjoyable experience by learners. Video movies provide topics and ideas for learners to discuss. In order to choose video material for the classroom, topics must be chosen based on students' interest and their level of English proficiency, as well as cultural aspects. It is easy for a group of imaginative teachers experienced in using video in ELT to sit down and draw up a list of different ways of using video in the classroom. There are many accounts where interesting video lessons are reported in the literature. Canning-Wilson (2000) suggests that as F/SL educators we must not lose sight of the educational purpose it has in the language classroom although it may be a popular tool to use with students. To get a successful result in language teaching using the video as an aid there are some techniques that should be benefited by both teacher and learner.

1. Active Viewing

Active viewing increases the students' enjoyment and satisfaction and focuses their attention on the main idea of the video presentation. So, it is necessary for students to take an active part in video teaching presentations. Before starting the presentation, the teacher writes some key questions on the board about the presentation so that the students get an overview of the content of it. After viewing the questions, the students answer the questions orally, or the students may take notes while viewing. For more detailed comprehension students are

provided a cue sheet or viewing guides and let them watch and listen for specific details or specific features of language. However, it should be kept in mind that the level of the students should be taken into account and adapt the technique according to their levels.

2. FREEZE FRAMING AND PREDICTION

Freeze framing means stopping the picture on the screen by pressing the still or pause button. Video gives us an additional dimension of information about the Characters' body language, facial expressions, emotions, reactions, and responses. Teacher freezes the picture when he or she wants to teach words and expressions regarding mood and emotions, to ask questions about a particular scene, or to call students' attention to some points. By freezing the scene, the students can be asked what is going to happen next. So, they speculate on what will happen in the next act. Freeze framing is excellent for speculation. This activity also fires the imagination of the students by leading them predicting and deducing further information about the characters.

3. SILENT VIEWING

As video is an audiovisual medium, the sound and the vision are separate components. Silent viewing arouses student interests, stimulates thought, and develops skills of anticipation. In silent viewing, the video segment is played with the sound off using only the picture. This activity can also be a prediction technique when students are watching video for the first time. One way of doing this is to play the video segment without the sound and tell students to observe the behavior of the characters and to use their power of deduction. Then press the pause button at intervals to stop the picture on the screen and get students to guess what is happening and what the characters might be saying or ask students what has happened up to that point. Finally, video segment is replayed with the sound on so that learners can compare their impressions with what actually happens in the video.

4. SOUND ON AND VISION OFF ACTIVITY

This activity can be interesting and useful to play a section of a video unit and

remove the visual element from the presentation by obscuring the picture so that students can hear only the dialogue but unable to see the action. Through this activity the students predict or reconstruct what has happened visually depending only what they hear.

5. REPETITION AND ROLE-PLAY

When there are some difficult language points in the video unit, closely repetition can be a necessary step to communicative production exercises. A scene on video is replayed with certain pauses for repetition either individually or in chorus. When students have a clear understanding of the presentation, they are asked to act out the scene using as much of the original version as they can remember. When students become confident with role playing and are sure of vocabulary and language structures, more creative activity can be introduced in which they are asked to improvise the scene to fit their views of the situation and the characters they are playing. Role-play involves students as active participants. As each student plays the assigned role, s/he becomes more and more involved. This activity also helps students to better understanding their own behavior and to be more able to respond in a positive way to various human relationships. In other words, role playing is a good communicative activity and true preparation for real-life situations. It gives a chance to students to apply what they are learning.

6. REPRODUCTION ACTIVITY

After students have seen a section, students are asked to reproduce either what is being said, to describe what is happening, or to write or retell what has happened. This activity encourages students to try out their knowledge. Students will benefit from experimenting in English, even though it is challenging and mistakes are made. As it seems a bit difficult to perform, guidance, help and reassurance may be needed.

7. DUBBING ACTIVITY

This activity can be done when students have the necessary language competence. In this activity, students are asked to fill in the missing dialogues after watching a sound-off video episode. It is interesting and enjoyable for the students to complete a scene from the video by dubbing.

8. FOLLOW-UP ACTIVITY

It is important that a video presentation should lead to follow-up activity as the basis for further extended oral practice. Discussion stimulates communication among students, and it helps to achieve communicative practice. With this activity students have an opportunity to develop sharing and co-operative skills.

Conclusion

Languages are not fixed but constantly changing, so is the media; television, radio and newspaper which are an extraordinarily rich source of language in use. In order to expose foreign language learners to the target language the use of technology need to be exploited in the classroom as much as possible. For that reason, a great tendency towards the use of technology and its integration into the curriculum developed by the foreign language teachers has gained a great importance. Particularly the use of video has received increasing attention in recent studies on technology integration into teacher education curriculum.

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